

A code search tool using text-based approach

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Abstract: Code reuse becomes an important opportunity for a software development organization, which helps in reuse of software component or code snippets which are already developed and well tested. It helps in reducing the cost and time in development of software. When effective and efficient, a code search can boost programmer productivity; however, the search effectiveness depends on the programmer's ability to specify a query that captures how the desired code may have been implemented. Further, the results often include many irrelevant matches that must be filtered manually. Our proposed code search tool can help better as it is language specific and also users can contribute their code fragments using this tool so that others can be fetched.

Keywords: Code search, Code clones, code detection techniques

1. Introduction

In software development activities, source code examples are critical for understanding concepts, applying fixes, improving performance, and extending software functionalities. Oftentimes, developers are looking for code fragments that offer similar code fragments. We have many search tools, but there is no search tool to search only python codes. The existing systems tutorials, lecture notes etc, but they do not provide error free code files all the time, hence clumsiness takes place. So, a search tool to search, share, execute and understand codes will be better. In existing systems, anyone can upload a code so it may contain errors. We propose a solution to discover code fragments implementing similarly. Everyone contributes their work. But there is no one to cross verify the codes. So, it may contain errors and it is difficult for users to identify whether the code is correct or wrong. Our search tool allows users to search for codes in free of cost as it is available freely through internet. User can also contact to give suggestions and can also give feedback. New codes can be added only by the admin and only admin have the right to update or delete any codes.

1.1 Code basic definitions

The code clones are separate fragments of code that are very similar and can be classified into following four types:

- Type-1 Exact clones: Identical code blocks except for variations in whitespace, design, and developer comments.
- Type-2 Renamed clones: Including Type-1 features along with syntactically identical code block.
- Type-3 Gapped clones: Containing Type-2 features and additional modifications such as some lines can be deleted. But outcomes are similar.
- Type-4 Semantic or logical clones: Provides an alternative approach to resolve the same issue. Such logically similar code twin is address here.

Although software cloning techniques is considered as bad practice in case of maintenance, but many programmers use them. We list some reasons behind software cloning.

- Limitations of programmer's skills and hard time constraints inhibit proper software evolution, which lead to copy-paste-modifying approach.
- The difficulty in understanding complex systems promotes to copying existing logic or functionality.
- sometimes programmers are forced to copy and paste code due to limitations in programming languages.
- Programmers often fear to bring in new ideas in existing software. They fear that introduction of new code may result in a lengthy software development life cycle. Furthermore, it is easier to reuse the existing code than to develop a fresh solution since new code may introduce new errors.

1.2 Merits of code clones

- Developers adapt code cloning technique as it is a fast and easy method of changing in requirements during the development of software.
- Few programming paradigms provides the use of templates in software implementation.

- If a programming language lack of reuse and abstraction, then this mechanism will help to enhance existing code fragments quickly.

1.3 Demerits of code clones

- Because of presence of code clones in software, increases the cost of maintenance.
- If a code fragment with bug copied at different places of logic, then it increases the probability of bug propagation. Code cloning leads to code deterioration and an increase in bugs as the system evolves.
- Code cloning discourages the use of refactoring, inheritance etc. so that it leads to bad impact on design.

2. Literature Survey

There are abundant techniques for searching of code snippets, there is an approach to define a grammar, which enumerate all derivations of the grammar, checking each one for consistency with the examples. This approach can be combined with pruning based on types and other logical reasoning (**Feser et al., 2015**) [1]. Another class of systems is based on Satisfiability Modulo Theories (SMT) solving. SMT combines SAT-style search with theories like arithmetic and inequalities, with the benefit that theory-dependant sub problems can be handled by special purpose solvers. Many program synthesis engines based on SMT solvers exist, e.g., Sketch (**Solar-Lezama, 2008**) [2] and Brahma (**Gulwani et al., 2011**) [3]. They convert the semantics of a DSL (Domain specific Languages) into a set of constraints between variables representing the program and then call an SMT solver to find a satisfying setting of the program variables. Finding similar code fragments beyond syntactic similarities has several uses in the field of software engineering. **Sirres, et.al., (2018)** [4] Proposed an approach COCABU to address vocabulary mismatch problem while search for code in the repositories, focuses to automatically expand developer code search queries (i.e. free-form queries) to retrieve relevant code elements. It is built from GitHub and Q&A posts from Stack OVERFLOW to find the most relevant source code examples for developer queries. Cocabu builds snippet index and code index to speed up the performance. User queries are augmented to accelerate search process by adding relevant API names, class or method names since search queries may not include them in general by developers, which lead to get less accurate search results. The current implementation of COCABU uses the scoring function implemented in the Lucene library. This function combines the Boolean Model (BM) and the Vector Space Model (VSM) to determine the relevancy of a document given for a user query. Apart from these search

techniques, we analyse the search engines for code. **Kisub kim et.al. (2018)** [5] elaborates FaCoY is statically finds code fragments which may be semantically and syntactically matches (type4) users input code. It follows two strategies query alternation and query structuring which is based on three indices are snippet index, code index, question index to ensure search speed and evaluation takes place between krugle, Searchcode, FaCoY using precision and recall. FaCoY must produce AST (Abstract Syntax Tree) of a code snippet to ensure accuracy. It uses Java language as input (Over Stackoverflow posts) and evaluated with the help of BigClone benchmark, IJaDataset using Precision@k metric and recall and compared with SourcererCC and DyCLINK. It can be useful in code/patch recommendation on buggy code in Defects4J benchmark. **Jadon (2016)** [6] proposed technique for clone detection identifies similar clones (Type-3) and quantify their similarity. C programs taken as input and then generates feature set as intermediate format which are passed through Libsvm tool for the classification of code snippet. Scaling is done to the train data and test data sets and then accuracy obtained by the tool. **Ragkhitwetsagul, et.al., (2017)** [7] proposed to exploit compilation and decompilation as a pre-processing step for detecting clones in Java programs. **Chen et.al., (2015)** [8] Proposed a technique to identify known android malware by using NiCad clone detector on java code and detects only Type-1, 2, 3 clones using malware families.

3. Methodology

Source code is treated as sequence of lines or strings, from that the code fragments are compared with each other and similar fragments are considered as code clone. Little transformation required for source code. They detect type1 clones more effectively. We propose a model, takes a code fragment from a user and searches in a software projects' code base to identify code fragments that are similar to the user's input. The search often returns fragments that are also syntactically similar to the input query.

Figure 1: Architecture diagram of search tool

When user posts a code, it will be executed against sample inputs and if the code executes successfully then the code gets uploaded by authorized person. Hence error free codes are available. Our code search tool implemented using Django which is python web framework helps in rapid development of applications. A common task of developer is to search for code in code databases with user input, this could be filtering a list of objects by a category. Categories are nothing but programming languages like python, java etc. Text-based fields have a selection of matching operations. We use `icontains()` method for the case insensitive match. The algorithm can be as follows-

Algorithm to search for code

function search(request):

```

q = request.GET.get('q') // q is code query given

post = Post.objects.filter(Q(posttitle__icontains=q)|
Q(postdetail__icontains=q)).distinct()

last_records = Post.objects.all().order_by('-id')[ :3]

category1 = Category.objects.all()

d = {'post': post,'category1': category1,'last_records':last_records}

return render(request, d)

```

The screenshot shows the user interface for the code search tool. It features a search bar with a 'Search for...' input field and a 'Go!' button. Below the search bar, there is a 'Categories' section listing 'Python' and 'Java'. At the bottom, there is a 'Recently Updated Codes' section listing items like 'print n', 'Text Alignment', and 'String Validators'.

Figure:2 code search interface

Algorithm to add categories of languages

```

function add_category(request):

    if not request.user.is_authenticated:

        //redirects to login authentication apge

        error = ""

    if request.method=="POST":

        cn = request.POST['catname']

        Category.objects.create(categoryname=cn)

        return render (request, d)

```


Figure 3: Adding language Categories to tool

The code fragments are of either python or java. Such contributed code posts are added under a category (Programming Language).

Algorithm to add user codes to the database

```

function add_post(request):

    if not request.user.is_authenticated:

        redirect('login')

        category = Category.objects.all()

        error = ""

    if request.method=="POST":

        // retrieves post details

        c1 = Category.objects.get(categoryname=c)

        post.objects.create(post_info)

        return render (request, d)

```


Figure 4: Contributing codes to tool

Admin can manage all the functionalities of tool, like handling contributed code posts under each category. Admin collects feedback from the user in the form of comments and he can

approve and disapprove such comments. Of course, maintaining all these functionalities of tool can be burden to the admin. So that in future we can automate it using learning algorithms.

Conclusion and Future Scope

Our code search tool provides various features, which complement the information system and increase the productivity of the system. These features make the system easily usable and convenient. Some of the important features are access to most required information, Data Security, Organized and structured storage of facts, No decay of old Records. In future this can be extended to other programming languages and more information can be provided so that user can search over a large database. We are looking into reducing the burden to administrator by automating the process using learning algorithms.

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